

(non-IACS) Monitoring systems for beneficiaries' compliance checks

OBJECTIVES AND CHALLENGES

As in the previous programming period, Member States are required to monitor the compliance of beneficiaries, also considering that new interventions (e.g. eco-schemes) and requirements (e.g. social conditionality) have been introduced. Yet, Member States are now called to **reduce the burden for farmers** and the administrative costs fostering the simplification of the monitoring systems, while improving their **ability to collect data at farm level**. All Member States largely rely on IACS systems to collect data about beneficiaries' compliance. Nonetheless, there are other (non-IACS) monitoring systems that can be established and complement IACS.

MAIN TOOLS ADOPTED: STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES

ClassyFarm (IT)

It operates as an integrated system for **categorising breeding based on risk factors**, utilising scientifically validated coefficients to convert collected data into a numerical risk indicator for farms. Methodological transparency is maintained through the public disclosure of the risk assessment and categorisation processes. One of the fundamental features is its **interoperability with other IT systems** such as the Livestock Registry, the Electronic Veterinary Prescription and the sanitary diagnostic laboratories.

It enhances the efficacy of data by making interoperable already existing administrative data sources.

It focuses only on specific areas, such as animal welfare, farm biosecurity, antimicrobial consumption, and antimicrobial susceptibility profiles.

LAD IT System (LV)

The tool is an IT system with **multiple subsystems and data exchange services** accessible to stakeholders, including the RSS, Ministry of Agriculture, and evaluators. It handles **extensive daily operations** and enables evaluators to access applicant data from other systems. Its workflow involves assessing needs, capturing and verifying data, structured management, and integrating with Oracle for efficient reporting to prevent system overload.

Acknowledged efficiency and effectiveness in managing agricultural data.

Technical and technological complexity.

Digital Farm Book - SIEX (ES)

This tool is designed to collect, store, and exchange information not only on the structure of the agricultural holding but also on the agricultural practices—from ploughing or harvesting to fertilizing and pesticides applications—that are performed on the parcel. The data in this tool provides farmers with a deeper understanding of their **operation's performance**. Additionally, when this information is shared with the competent authority, it can serve as **evidence of compliance** with certain CAP requirements.

The tool provides farmer with valuable information on their holding's performance and it assists in verifying that they meet the requirements for receiving aid.

The tool primarily contributes to environmental objectives (SO4, SO5, SO6), and the cross-cutting objective, with unclear ideas of its contribution to the remaining objectives.

